

USE OF MICRO-CT TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF VOIDING AND FIBRE MISALIGNMENT ON KINK-BAND FORMATION

PhD student: Jiraphant Srisuriyachot, University of Bath

Email: js2580@bath.ac.uk

Supervisors: Alexander Lunt, Richard Butler, Jean Bénézech and Guillaume Couégnat

**Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council**

CERTIFICATION
FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE
TESTING PYRAMID

18/05/2023

Introduction – Compressive failure

Fibre kinking

(a) Characteristic constitutive response of fiber kinking theory

(b) Schematic idealization of a kink band

Bergan, A et al. (2020)

Introduction – Imperfection

Fibre waviness/misalignment
+
Existing of voids

Micro-buckling of fibre

Introduction – Research gaps

Post-mortem analysis

- SEM/TEM/FIB

Gutkin, R et al. (2010)

Experiment – Sample geometry

Offset geometry

- Addition shear loading - More stable failure
- No addition device
- Geometry symmetry

Manufacturing conditions

- Standard pressure – baseline
- Low pressure – defect sample

Notch

- Localised damage area

Addition plies

- Prevent out-of-plane buckling

Schematic of offset angle compressive testing adopted from Pimenta et al. (2009)

Experiment – Synchrotron setup

Experiment – Synchrotron setup

Phase contrast enhancement in CFRPs

Results – CT images

Baseline sample

Defect sample

Image Processing

Synchrotron μ CT of UD CFRPs with a notch

Kink-band formation in the presence of micro defects

Image processing

Fibre misalignment orientation analysis

$\theta_{\text{in-plane}}$

10°
8°
6°
4°
2°
0°
-2°
-4°

Void identification

Fibre angle after failure

Localised strain field analysis

Predestined failure

In-plane Shear

0.013
0
-0.01
-0.02
-0.03

Digital volume correlation before failure

This block contains three main visualizations within a red dashed border. On the left, a color-coded map shows fiber misalignment orientation, with a color scale from -4° to 10°. A red arrow points to a specific region labeled 'Void identification'. Below this is the text 'Fibre angle after failure'. On the right, a color-coded map shows the localized strain field, with a color scale for 'In-plane Shear' from -0.03 to 0.013. A red arrow points to a region labeled 'Predestined failure'. Below this is the text 'Digital volume correlation before failure'.

Results – Void segmentation

Results – Fibre orientation development

Results – Digital Volume Correlation

Results – Summaries

Baseline sample

Defect sample

Results – Summaries

Without void

With void

Results – DVC sensitivity analysis

Conclusion

- Synchrotron μ CT with enhanced phase contrast
 - Reveals individual fibres (random speckle pattern)
 - Fibre misalignment orientation
 - 3D strain field mapping with a global approach DVC
- Detailed characterisation of CFRP damage mechanisms
 - Combined shear and compressive shear \rightarrow Bending \rightarrow kink-band formation
 - Unsupported region (e.g. void, matrix cracking) \rightarrow fibre lose instability
- 'Real' boundary condition and geometry effects for future FE simulation

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

CERTIFICATION
FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE
TESTING PYRAMID

AIRBUS

BAE SYSTEMS

Rolls-Royce

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**